

Diversity in Aviation at Bridgewater State University

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Abstract—The aviation industry continues to face persistent inequities in gender and racial representation, with only 10.8% of pilots globally identifying as women and 7.6% as people of color in the United States. These disparities stem from systemic barriers—including high training costs, limited mentorship and representation, and restricted access to aviation resources—that disproportionately affect women, students of color, and other historically excluded groups. Bridgewater State University (BSU), home to Massachusetts’ only four-year degree program in flight training, has strategically addressed these barriers to diversify the future aviation workforce.

This study examines BSU’s comprehensive approach to broadening participation in aviation through three interrelated strategies: (1) Cost mitigation, including subsidized fleet and simulator rates, targeted scholarships such as the Ricciardi Aviation Scholarship, and the Summer Start Program, which provides free ground school and simulator access; (2) Mentorship and representation, supported through partnerships with the Organization of Black Aerospace Professionals (OBAP), Women in Aviation (WAI), and BSU’s Gateway to the Airways program for regional middle and high school students; and (3) Resource investment, including a university-owned fleet of 13 aircraft, six Redbird simulators, and expanded curricular offerings.

Enrollment data show steady increases in both female students (from 9.8% in 2020 to 14.3% in 2025) and students of color (from 28% to 33.3%), surpassing national averages. This progress reflects BSU’s intentional integration of equity into program design, infrastructure investment, and student support structures. By reducing financial barriers, strengthening community networks, and expanding access to high-quality flight training, BSU offers a replicable model for higher education institutions seeking to advance diversity, equity, and inclusion in aviation education and workforce development.

Keywords—aviation education, diversity, equity, workforce development, flight training, higher education, mentorship, representation

I. INTRODUCTION

Bridgewater State University’s aviation flight program, “Provides comprehensive flight training and aviation management education, encourages lifelong learning, and prepares our graduates to be aviation leaders serving the dynamic aviation industry in Massachusetts and beyond (Aviation Science Department Mission, 2025)”. This mission speaks to BSU’s commitment, not only to the aviation industry but also to the New England region. As the only four-year degree program in flight training in the Commonwealth of Massachusetts, BSU has demonstrated its ability to diversify the aviation community while simultaneously maintaining rigorous academic standards, evidenced by its accreditation from Aviation Accreditation Board International (ABBI). However, this feat has not been easy to accomplish, especially given the challenges that aviation education has historically faced for non-traditional student populations. Specifically, issues surrounding cost, mentorship/representation, and access to aviation resources have limited the ability for female students, students of color, and other marginalized populations to enter the aviation industry.

The aviation industry has long been characterized by a pilot workforce that is predominantly white male, with limited inclusion of females or persons of color. According to the Women in Aviation Organization (WIA), as of December 31, 2024, there are 848,770 pilots globally, of which only 91,694 pilots (i.e., 10.8%) are women (Current statistics of women in aviation careers in the U.S.). With respect to pilots of color, the representation is even more stark. Of the 211,000 pilots in the United States, only 7.6% are pilots of color, and 3.9% are black pilots (Williams-Brown, 2024). Both of these statistical measures demonstrate a relatively low level of representation, especially given that the first woman to take flight occurred in 1908 (nearly five years after the Wright brothers’ initial flight), and the first black pilot to take flight occurred in 1912 (only nine

years after the Wright brothers' initial flight). Now that we are in the 21st century, the aviation industry should have achieved more gender and racial diversity. The lack of both gender and racial diversity in aviation speaks to the systemic discrimination inherent in the aviation industry.

One of the factors that perpetuates systemic discrimination in aviation is the cost of flight training. As we will demonstrate below, the expensive nature of flight training, coupled with historical wealth gaps for women and people of color, means that these populations struggle to pay for flight fees and therefore cannot enter the pilot workforce. As a result, they are often limited to lower-paying aviation careers and are kept out of the higher-paying jobs, such as pilots. To overcome this challenge, BSU has implemented several financial assistance programs to address the high cost of flight training.

However, helping minoritized populations pay for flight training resolves only one aspect of their challenges. Mentorship is also an important factor in helping women and people of color achieve their goal of becoming pilots. Representation by women and people of color in leadership roles within aviation helps them to visualize themselves as pilots. BSU has developed and supported organizations on campus to provide mentorship and community for female students and students of color within the aviation major.

Finally, the last barrier to increasing diversity in aviation is access to resources. Resources like aircraft, simulators, and flight instructors are not always available within the public sector. Most flight training is provided by private flight schools, which must be able to make a profit in the flight training business. This profit motive often translates into a cost structure that is too expensive for the first-generation students, who are typically students of color.

This research paper will examine how Bridgewater State University has tackled these issues within its flight training program. With a strategic focus on cost reduction, diversity, and acquisition of aviation resources, BSU has been able to significantly increase the number of students who can participate in the aviation industry. The successes outlined in this paper can serve as a model for other flight training programs that desire to impact workforce diversity in aviation positively.

II. COST OF FLIGHT TRAINING

BSU plays a crucial role in addressing the cost challenges faced by students in the southeast region of Massachusetts seeking flight training education. As a public institution of higher education, BSU receives some funding support from the state, which allows the university to subsidize, to some extent, the tuition/fees of matriculating aviation students. This subsidization is evident in how BSU sets its flight fees, which tend to be lower than average. Overall, BSU has the lowest rates with respect to the aircraft's hourly fleet cost and the instructor's hourly rate. Table 1 compares the cost across various public and private flight training institutions for students to rent an aircraft, utilize a flight instructor for training, and operate an FAA-approved Advanced Aviation Training Device (AATD), i.e., simulator.

TABLE 1 COSTS OF FLIGHT TRAINING

University	Public/Private	Fleet Rate	Airplane Type	Instructor Rate	Simulator
Bridgewater State University	Public	\$160	Skyhawk Cessna 172	\$63	\$83
Embry-Riddle Aeronautical University	Private	\$205	Skyhawk Cessna 172	\$83	\$162
Auburn University	Public	\$265	Skyhawk Cessna 172	\$65	\$120
South Dakota State University	Public	\$210	Skyhawk Cessna 172	\$75	\$70
Florida Tech University	Private	\$179	Piper Warrior	Call them	\$65

As you can see from Table 1, our prices are generally lower than most BSU competitors in America. The hourly cost for BSU translates into a total cost of rating/licenses, as indicated in Table 2.

TABLE 2 BSU ESTIMATED RATING/LICENSES FEES FOR FLIGHT COURSES (Based on course minimum hours)

Private Pilot License	\$13,744.00
Instrument Rating	\$14,255.00
Commercial Pilot-Single Engine	\$12,134.00
Flight Instructor	\$10,140.00

BSU also offers a Summer Start Program that provides a free Private-Pilot ground school course and intensive flight opportunities for new aviation students to enhance their proficiency in flight training. This free course equates to a \$1,500 scholarship. (BSU Tuition/Fees) In addition to the free course, students in the Summer Start Program receive other financial benefits, such as a continental breakfast, a hot lunch, procedure trainers, a course training binder, and free access to the AATD simulators, communication simulators, and VR training. These benefits enable students to achieve greater flight proficiency, foster community, and progress more quickly through the Private Pilot Rating.

BSU not only has the lowest cost, but they have also stepped up in helping students achieve their dream by providing check ride scholarships. Created in 2019, the Louis M. Ricciardi '81

Aviation Science Scholarship Fund has helped over 231 students obtain financial support for their FAA check rides, which are typically not funded by their financial aid. Students automatically qualify for this scholarship, and it is not tied to need or merit. With the Ricciardi Aviation Scholarship, students are reimbursed up to \$400 each for the Private Pilot, Instrument, and Commercial Pilot check rides. As for the Certified Flight Instructor Rating, students are reimbursed up to \$800 for that check ride. Table 3 shows the reimbursements provided.

TABLE 3 BSU AVIATION SCHOLARSHIPS AWARDED, 2019-2024

Academic Year	Total Scholarships Awarded	Number of Students Awarded
2019	\$20,800	43
2020	\$17,200	35
2021	\$21,600	49
2022	\$15,600	37
2023	\$5,200	11
2024	\$22,900	54
Total	\$103,300	231

Most recently, in 2025, BSU received a new bequest from the Jean Harley Estate, which will provide an endowed scholarship for aviation students.

The final cost-mitigation support that BSU provides is the hiring of our students/alums as Certified Flight Instructors (CFIs). Students who come to work at BSU receive several benefits: they receive wages that are significantly higher than the \$15-minimum wage rate (i.e., they are paid \$28-\$32 per hour), they are given free professional development (i.e., BSU provides training for CFIs to obtain their CFII/MEI rating), and they can build flight hours that count toward their ATP minimum (1,000-1,500 pilot-in-command hours).

III. MENTORSHIP/REPRESENTATION IN THE FLIGHT DEPARTMENT AT BSU

As noted above, the aviation industry has a limited degree of diversity and is predominantly comprised of white, male pilots. In an industry characterized by the minimal presence of female pilots or pilots of color, the role of mentorship becomes important. Fortunately, BSU plays a critical role in addressing the lack of diversity. Through its student recruitment efforts, BSU has successfully educated and trained a diverse cohort of pilots, as demonstrated in Table 4.

TABLE 4 PERCENTAGES OF FEMALE STUDENTS AND STUDENTS OF COLOR IN AVIATION AT BSU

Academic Year	Total Students Enrolled	Percent of Female Students	Percent of Students of Color	Covid Affected Year
Spring 2020	143	9.8%	28.0%	No
Spring 2021	157	7.0%	26.8%	Yes
Spring 2022	150	8.7%	30.7%	Yes
Spring 2023	169	12.4%	33.1%	No
Spring 2024	178	14.6%	31.5%	No
Spring 2025	126	14.3%	33.3%	No

You will note that the percentage of female students in the flight training program increased from 9.8% in Spring 2020 to 14.3% in Spring 2025. A similar increase occurred for students of color, which increased from 28% in Spring 2020 to 33.3% in Spring 2025; this represents an increase of 4.5 percentage points in the enrollment of female students and 5.3 percentage points in the enrollment of students of color. When compared to the industry averages of 10.8% and 7.6%, respectively, BSU has been a productive educational partner in diversifying aviation.

BSU has also partnered with mentorship programs such as the Organization of Black Aerospace Professionals (OBAP) and Women in Aviation (WAI). With these programs in place, students can get firsthand mentorships from individuals who are actively working in their field. In addition, BSU has created its own program called Gateway to the Airways (G2TA), which brings middle- and high-school students from regional school districts that have been traditionally underserved. Students in the G2TA program spend six weeks at BSU, where they get hands-on experience in aviation STEM topics such as aerodynamics, weight and balance, and aviation safety. They also learn about aviation careers and participate in field trips to regional and international airports.

Finally, the Aviation Science Department has established its own Aviation Industry Advisory Board (AIAB) to help the university stay current in the aviation field. One of the subcommittees of AIAB focuses on diversifying aviation. This subcommittee is tasked with creating opportunities for underrepresented student groups to access aviation careers. They also work with charitable organizations to help fund students' aviation costs.

IV. EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES

For any aviation program, the investment in resources helps to maintain the safety, currency, and relevance of flight training; Bridgewater State University is no exception. Since the inception of the aviation program in 1980, BSU has offered a BS in Aviation Science, with two concentrations: Aviation Flight and Aviation Management. At that time, BSU did not own its

own fleet of aircraft; instead, it signed an agreement with Wiggins Airways of Norwood, MA, to provide flight training to its students. However, to ensure high-quality training standards, BSU decided to purchase its own fleet of aircraft in 2007, starting with 8 Cessna 172R Skyhawks, 2 Piper Arrows, 1 Piper Seneca multi-engine aircraft, and 1 stationary Redbird Simulator. In addition, they pursued Part 141 certification from the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA).

Today, BSU has increased its investment in aviation resources; they have now acquired 13 Cessna 172R Skyhawks, 1 Diamond DA-42, and 6 Redbird Simulators, including one full-motion simulator. They have also expanded their curriculum to include Dispatch Licenses and Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) certificates.

TABLE 5 BSU’S AIRCRAFT

Year Model	Manufacturer Name	Model	Aircraft Type
1997	CESSNA	172R	Single Engine Standard
2000	CESSNA	172R	Single Engine Standard
2000	CESSNA	172R	Single Engine Standard
2000	CESSNA	172R	Single Engine Standard
2000	CESSNA	172R	Single Engine Standard
2000	CESSNA	172R	Single Engine Standard
1997	CESSNA	172R	Single Engine Standard
1999	CESSNA	172R	Single Engine Standard
2000	CESSNA	172R	Single Engine Standard
1998	CESSNA	172R	Single Engine Standard
2003	CESSNA	172S	Single Engine Technically Advanced Aircraft (TAA)
2000	CESSNA	172S	Single Engine Technically Advanced Aircraft (TAA)

2004	CESSNA	172S	Single Engine Technically Advanced Aircraft (TAA)
2005	DIAMOND	DA-42	Multi Engine Complex Aircraft (TAA)

BSU’s investment is not limited to tangible assets or expansion of academic programs. They have also invested in student success. New student enrollment is currently limited to 56 incoming students so that they can develop a one-on-one relationship with professors. BSU has also provided free academic tutoring for students who may need support throughout their training or ground schools. The Chief Flight Instructor schedules a group study session twice a year to help students prepare for their oral section of their flight exams with the FAA.

Investment in student success takes place not only during matriculation, but also after graduation. BSU has cultivated industry partnerships that provide our students with entry-level career opportunities. Companies such as JetBlue, Cape Air, Endeavour, Envoy, Mountain Air Cargo, and FedEx work closely with BSU to recruit our students through gateway and cadet programs. With these resources, students are well-prepared for greatness throughout their university training and beyond, as they transition into the pilot workforce and the broader aviation industry.

V. CONCLUSION

With the many layoffs and furloughs that took place during the pandemic, there is no better time to diversify the aviation industry. Bridgewater State University is doing its part to contribute to that diversification. By mitigating the cost of aviation, creating mentorship/representation within its program, and providing a comprehensive array of aviation resources, BSU has effectively brought female students and students of color into aviation, a field that needs significant diversification.

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Kendell French, a proud native of St. Croix (U.S.V.I.), moved to Boston, Massachusetts in 2017 with aspirations of becoming a pilot. Now a senior at Bridgewater State University, he’s pursuing a double major in Aviation Science and Film and Video Art Production, with a minor in Digital Media. Kendell holds a commercial pilot

license and drone pilot licenses. He is also pursuing his certified flight instructor license at Bridgewater State University.

On campus, he works in the President’s Office and captures events as a student photographer, using visual storytelling to inspire. He was nominated to the Aviation Industry Advisory Board and uses his platform, @fly_french, to share flight content and motivate aspiring aviators—especially students of color.

Kendell is a first-generation college student and will also be the first pilot in his family. Kendell prides himself on breaking barriers while encouraging others to continue to aim high and pursue their goals and dreams. In his downtime, he enjoys bowling and playing drums and piano.